

Weddell Sea Observatory of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Change – WOBEC Data

Management Plan

Technical Documentation

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DRAFT

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Versions

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Project summary and administrative details

The overarching research goal will be to develop an efficient monitoring strategy to measure change and distinguish trends from natural variability in the EWS. With an evidence-based approach, WOBECE will address this goal by considering stakeholder knowledge and requirements and applying the best available scientific and technological knowledge. The following specific research questions (RQ) will guide the implementation of the project:

1. What is the baseline status of biodiversity and ecosystem functions within the EWS?
2. Which data and knowledge are needed to assess status, trends and mitigation measures in biodiversity changes and ecosystem services, and to identify areas of specific vulnerability and climate refugia?
3. How can the analysis of biodiversity, ecosystem functions and their relationship with environmental drivers improve future management of this changing ecosystem?

Project name: Weddell Sea Observatory of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Change (WOBECE)

Funding: Biodiversa+

Partners: Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI)
Antarctic and Southern Ocean Coalition (ASOC)
Institute of Natural Sciences (INS)
Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences (IOPAS)
Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI)
Stockholm University (SU)
University of Rostock (UR)
UiT The Arctic University of Norway (UIT)
University of Groningen (UG)
University of Padua (UP)
Wageningen Marine Research (WMR)

Definitions

Data: A set of values, symbols, or signs (recorded on any type of medium) that describe one or more properties of an entity. For example, the numbers generated by a sensor, values derived from a model or analysis, text entered into a survey, audio or video files, or the raw text of a document. Generally speaking, data are used to quantitatively or qualitatively describe one or more persons, objects or events. Research data provide the evidence base for supporting or refuting ideas in a scientific manner.

Data Management Plan: A document describing how an individual collection of data or linked data collections (e.g. under a single project or programme) will be managed, described, and stored, the standards the data conform to, and how data will be handled and protected during and after the completion of the project.

Information: Products derived from data that lead to a greater understanding of an entity. For example, the interpretation of a range of data from an array of conductivity sensors that informs us about the ocean's salinity range, or the narrative text of a report on algal blooms that informs the reader regarding their timing.

Metadata: Metadata provide information that describe the data source, and the time, place, and conditions under which the data were created. Metadata inform the user of who, when, what, where, why, and how data were generated. Metadata allow the data to be traced to a known origin and known quality. Metadata can be used for discovery and identification of data collections, to provide information on structural aspects of the data, and to provide administrative information on aspects such as ownership and licensing.

1. Data Policy

The WOBECE project is a collaborative, international project aimed at establishing representative monitoring stations on the eastern flank of the Weddell Sea and assessing ongoing community and environmental change across these stations through the forthcoming decades through a series of research expeditions and deployments of moored equipment.

To maximise the applicability of the collected data for the scientific community and society, professional coordination and data sharing across decades are envisioned. A transparent Data Policy is essential to achieving the WOBECE monitoring and scientific objectives, facilitating collaboration, and enabling broad use and impact of the WOBECE legacy data.

The WOBECE data Policy builds on the principles set forth in “Alignment of Polar Data Policies – Recommended Principles” (2021), the SCAR data Policy (2022) and the MOSAIC data policy. These are the overarching principles that guide how data is collected, preserved and shared between project partners and others.

3.1 Data must be ethically open

WOBECE data will be made accessible in a full, free, and open manner for all users in keeping with Section III.1.c. of the Antarctic Treaty, excepting cases where data must be limited for ethical, cultural, or legal reasons. Data should be “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”

3.2 Data should be free

Distribution and reuse of WOBECE data should be free of charge, delivered at no more than the cost of reproduction and delivery. With modern digital communication technologies, the distribution costs for modest data volumes have largely been eliminated, and typically do not justify any cost recovery on the distributor side. The costs of open data processes should be regarded as an intrinsic part of the cost of doing the research, and supported appropriately.

Where the management and handling of very large data volumes (“big data”) may incur significant costs and such costs cannot be funded as part of the original research activity or through the operating budget of the data centre, some cost recovery may be justified even under a free and open access data policy.

3.3 Data must be provided in a timely manner

Data must be published as soon as practicable following collection, in near real-time if possible, unless access is limited on the basis of §3.1, or if necessary to support reasonable ethical, cultural, legal, operational (including data processing, quality control, and documentation), or scholarly requirements. Such data embargoes should be applied only for good cause and for the shortest time feasible to allow for good data processing practices and to respect the scientific endeavours of data creators. For WOBE data, a maximum 2-year embargo limit should be provided, along with documented reasons for the embargoed status. This embargo can be extended based on the restrictions defined above. It is the responsibility of the data provider to request an extension in a timely manner, this request should include an argumentation why the embargo needs to be maintained. If not provided in a timely manner the data may be published.

3.4 FAIR Principles should be applied to the greatest extent practicable

To the greatest extent practicable, data should be made findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable¹, subject to §2.1.

3.5 All data must be accompanied by a complete set of metadata

Data collected as part of WOBE must be accompanied by complete metadata, compliant with DIF or ISO-19115 standards or relevant domain specific standards. Complete metadata must contain sufficient information to understand, access, and replicate the data set to a level of quality, accuracy, and precision specified in the metadata. Metadata elements should provide a clear description of the data; their provenance, the data structure; calibrations; and methods, including units, associated errors, or other limitations where possible. Whenever possible, data and metadata should include spatial and temporal attribution, in order to enhance their interoperability and suitability for broader use. The metadata must also contain information to support appropriate attribution. Metadata should be public, even if the associated data cannot be made public. It shall allow coupling users, software, and computing resources to the data. As a result, metadata must be machine-readable and interpretable as well as human-understandable.

3.6 Data should have persistent and globally unique identifiers

SCAR data should be assigned persistent and globally unique identifiers (PID) that remain linked to the data through republication or data aggregation processes, to facilitate unequivocal identification, attribution, data citation, provenance tracking, linking data with scientific results, and tracking distribution and impact of data collections. Examples of relevant PIDs include Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for unambiguously linking to data objects, or Open Researcher and Contributor Identifiers (ORCID) for unambiguously linking to individual researchers.

3.7 Data must be labelled as reusable

Data collected in the framework of WOBEC must be labelled as reusable by attaching a rights waiver, a public domain statement, or an internationally recognised data licence to the data. Data licences should be non-restrictive, specifying that the data may be re-used, with no requirement more onerous than an acknowledgement of the data's source – for example, the Creative Commons Open Attribution Licence (CC-BY). Where possible, the rights waiver or licence should be assigned by the owner or source of the data, and these parties should be identified in accompanying metadata.

3.8 Data sources should be attributable and attributed

Users of WOBEC data should formally acknowledge data authors and sources.

3.9 Data must be appropriately preserved for the long term

WOBEC Partners must ensure that WOBEC data held by them are preserved so that they are enduring, resilient to corruption or loss, and remain accessible via appropriate data and metadata repositories.

3.10 Data management and long-term curation must be planned and resourced

WOBEC will develop a Data Management Plan. The Data Management Plan will describe procedures in place to ensure that the data will retain its value over the long-term, and the data will be curated effectively in a trusted manner. The WOBEC Data Management Plan will be open for review by the Project partners, the relevant National Antarctic Data Centres or other relevant entities.

3.11 Quality assurance and fitness-for-purpose

Data providers are responsible for any quality assurance and quality control required to meet community standards. Data users are responsible for ensuring that the data they use is fit-for-purpose.

3.12 Data sharing between Project Partners

Prior to publication of WOBEC data to online repositories and the granting of 'open access' data rights, data will be made available to other participants by the WOBEC project board (on request). This sharing of data will be carried out under the proviso that the data collector (or collecting group) are offered the chance to collaborate on the scientific analysis and be offered co-authorship based on the principles described in section "Authorship and Acknowledgment"

below. The data provider and/or data PI may object to the usage of data in a publication if that publication conflicts with his or her own publication strategy. Any such objection must be discussed and agreed upon in writing with the WOBECE project board. The data provider and/or data PI may not object to the usage of data beyond the public release date.

3.13 Authorship and Acknowledgment

Generally, co-authorship on publications and other public documentation must be offered to those that have made a substantial contribution following the principles of good scientific practice. An inclusive co-authorship approach is encouraged. Accordingly, co-authorship on publications and other public documentation must generally be offered to those that have made a substantial contribution to a) the intellectual conception or design of research; b) the acquisition, analysis, or interpretation of the data (i.e., including the data provider or data PI), or c) the drafting or significant revision of the work.

Lead authors have the ultimate decision authority and responsibility to identify and appropriately engage co-authors.

Contributors to the work that do not warrant co-authorship should be identified by name in the acknowledgments.

WOBECE data must be acknowledged or referenced in publications and other public documentation, specifically including relevant digital object identifiers, data providers (if not co-authors), and funding agencies.

All publications and other public documentation using WOBECE data must include a funding acknowledgment of WOBECE in general in the following form:

"Data used in this manuscript was produced as part of the WOBECE project".

4. Data Summary

4.1 Purpose of the data collection/generation

- What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

4.2 Relation to the objectives of the project

Parameter	Habitat/Ecosystem	Devices
Species Abundance	Seafloor Sediment Ecosystems	Observation and sampling tools
	Upper Ocean	Plankton nets, microscopes, automated counters
	Water Column	Plankton nets, microscopes, automated counters
Biodiversity	Seafloor Sediment Ecosystems	Taxonomic analysis tools, eDNA analysis
Metabolic Rate (O₂ flux)	Seafloor Sediment Ecosystems	Oxygen sensors, respirometers
Samples (Frozen Tissue)	Seafloor Sediment Ecosystems	Sampling tools, cryogenic storage
	Sea Ice	Sampling tools, cryogenic storage
Molecular Analysis	Seafloor Sediment Ecosystems	DNA/RNA extraction kits, sequencing equipment
	Sea Ice	DNA/RNA extraction kits, sequencing equipment
Chlorophyll (Chl-a concentration)	Seafloor Sediment Ecosystems	Fluorometers, spectrophotometers
Chlorophyll (Upper Ocean Chl-a)	Upper Ocean	Fluorometers, spectrophotometers
Chlorophyll (Chl-a, Phaeophytin)	Upper Ocean	Fluorometers, spectrophotometers
	Water Column	Fluorometers, spectrophotometers
Chlorophyll (Sea Ice Chl-a)	Sea Ice	Fluorometers, spectrophotometers
Biogeochemical Variables	Seafloor Sediment Ecosystems	Biogeochemical sensors, incubation chambers
	Upper Ocean	Biogeochemical sensors, incubation chambers
	Sea Ice	Biogeochemical sensors, flow cytometry, incubation chambers
	Water Column	Biogeochemical sensors, incubation chambers
	Cross-Habitat	Biogeochemical sensors, incubation chambers
Nutrients	Upper Ocean	Nutrient analyzers, spectrophotometers
	Water Column	Nutrient analyzers, spectrophotometers
Environmental Data	Sea Ice	Temperature loggers, salinity probes, texture analyzers
Distribution (Echo Backscatter)	Upper Ocean	Echosounders, sonar systems
Size/Weight (Fish)	Upper Ocean	Measuring boards, balances, scales
Protist Samples	Upper Ocean, Sea Ice	Sampling bottles, microscopes

Genetic Data	Seafloor Sediment Ecosystems	Sequencing equipment, bioinformatics tools
	Upper Ocean	Sequencing equipment, bioinformatics tools
	Sea Ice	Sequencing equipment, bioinformatics tools
	Water Column	Sequencing equipment, bioinformatics tools
	Cross-Habitat	Sequencing equipment, bioinformatics tools, physiological proxies
Physiological Data	Cross-Habitat	Physiological sensors, respirometers
Protist Biodiversity	Cross-Habitat	Microscopes, eDNA sampling kits, sequencing equipment

2.3 Types and formats of data generated/collected

- What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect

Within the frame of WOBECE, a diverse array of data will be collected, encompassing biological information on species within water masses, as well as physical, chemical, and dynamic characteristics of the ocean, atmosphere, and cryosphere.

Self-describing file formats such as NetCDF, HDF/HDF5, and Darwin Core Archives will be utilized. When appropriate, NERC Controlled Vocabularies will be used. In cases where no clear standard can be identified, dedicated effort will be made to identify a common approach for those data.

WOBECE will collect and make accessible previously acquired data from monitoring programs and research projects focussing on the Weddell Sea ecosystem. Some of these data will be critical as the baseline conditions for evaluating change in the region. In circumstances where such data do not yet exist in repositories, efforts will be undertaken to recover them and make them available as part of the project legacy. The focus of the DMP is the newly collected datasets for this preliminary version.

For each type of sampling method or experiment, a standard operating procedure (SOP) will be developed and continuously updated to assure consistency and accuracy. Each version will get a DOI and the latest versions will be listed in the DMP (this document).

The SOP outlines a comprehensive set of step-by-step instructions for conducting a specific experiment. It includes the necessary preparatory steps, calibration procedures, required conditions, the experimental process, and subsequent processing steps. Upon completion, the experimental data will be cleaned and formatted to a standard (if feasible), with all relevant metadata either included in the same file or provided in a separate metadata file.

The Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) will be published and assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to ensure their accessibility and citation in academic and professional contexts.

- How is the original data gathered and stored on board and how do you transfer it to shore?

The data responsible person/group as indicated in the SOP holds the primary responsibility to gather all necessary files and documents at the end of the cruise and deliver the data to the responsible data center.

The data will be provided in a tidy format and, when possible, making use of templates and/or existing standards.- What processing on the raw data do you plan? Please differentiate between data quality assurance (handling of outliers, missing and suspect values, null observations) and data harmonisation (code, label and QC flag explanations, consistent use of headers, data formatting, conforming to standards).

Currently not available

- When do you plan to perform these processing steps?

Currently not available. Discussions will be held with the responsible researchers to establish a realistic and manageable timeframe for completing the processing.

- What is the expected size (Megabyte to Terabyte range) of the data?

Most datasets below 1GB, with couple of exceptions:

DNA sequencing: 3TB
Sediment ecosystem study: 10TB (video)
Hydroacoustic 14 TB/expedition

- Who will be the principal users of the data? Users are both active (those that clean up or analyse the data) and passive (those that read or assess the data).

Sample collection

The use of the Nansen Legacy Logger and label printer is currently being explored. This tool could greatly assist in ensuring accurate and correct information, thereby reducing the risk of sample loss.

Data Accessibility

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- What naming conventions for your data files will you follow?

When possible, a standardized naming format is advised. Currently, the following format is proposed:

{YYYYMMDD}_WOBEC_WP{NB}_{DESCRIPTIVE_ACRONYM}_{COLLECTOR}.{EXTENSION}

A list with descriptive acronyms will be composed and made available online.- Can you list some search keywords? The purpose of keywords is to optimize the findability of the datasets. The following keywords from GCMD thesaurus (<https://gcmd.earthdata.nasa.gov/KeywordViewer/>) will be added to datasets to improve its findability:

SOUTHERN OCEAN, WEDDELL SEA, ANTARCTICA, R/V POLARSTERN, MARINE ECOSYSTEMS, MARINE ENVIRONMENT MONITORING, BIODIVERSITY FUNCTIONS

Other keywords that are relevant but not found in the GCMD thesaurus include:WOBEC, Antarctica, Marine protected area, biodiversity, ecosystem, ...

- Do you foresee a need for different versions of the data? Both for your own internal use and when publishing the data? E.g. for some analyses the data might need reorganisation from a common ancestor. Which versioning scheme do you have in mind?

Currently not available

Making data openly accessible

- All data will be made openly available by default. Are there datasets for which you want to request an embargo (2 years from the end of data collection or end of project, whichever is shorter). Can you provide some argumentation why this embargo is needed?

Currently not available

- Do you plan to make the data and metadata available on repositories (an institutional, national or general data repository)? (national obligations are indicated in yellow)

Repository Name	Thematic/General Repository	Required Metadata Format(s)
GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility)	Thematic	Darwin Core, Dublin Core

OBIS (Ocean Biodiversity Information System)	Thematic	Darwin Core, EML
SCAR Antarctic Biodiversity Portal	Thematic	Darwin Core, Dublin Core
GenBank	Thematic	GenBank-specific format, Dublin Core
Antarctic Master Directory	Thematic	ISO 19115, Dublin Core
NCBI (National Center for Biotechnology Information)	Thematic	GenBank-specific format, Dublin Core
PANGAEA	General	Dublin Core, EML (Ecology Metadata Language)
Zenodo	General	DataCite, Dublin Core
Dryad	General	DataCite, Dublin Core
Repository University of Groningen	General	Dublin Core
Norwegian Polar Data Center	Thematic	Dublin Core, ISO 19115

Metadata standards

- which standards will be used for the metadata?

Metadata for the project will be created in accordance with the ISO 19115 standard. This ensures that all metadata will be consistent, comprehensive, and compatible with international geospatial data requirements. Metadata for each data set should follow the FAIR data principles in terms of fitness for purpose and fitness for re-use. The metadata should where appropriate follow current standards:

Oceanography, climatology, and modelling.

- o ISO 19115: A standard for presenting geographic information and services. It provides information about the identification, the extent, the quality, the spatial and temporal schema, spatial reference, and distribution of digital geographic data.

- o ISO 19115-2: An Imagery and gridded data standard expansion of ISO 19115.

Biology

- o Ecological Metadata Language (EML): A metadata specification that is used to document environmental data from almost any scientific domain, and includes sections for describing spatial, temporal, thematic, and taxonomic coverage of datasets.

- o Darwin Core: A body of standards, including a glossary of terms (in other contexts these might be called properties, elements, fields, columns, attributes, or concepts) intended to facilitate the sharing of information about biological diversity by providing reference definitions, examples, and commentaries.

o MIxS: Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence: The MIxS is a unified standard developed by the Genomic Standards Consortium (GSC) for reporting of minimum information about any (x) nucleotide sequence. It consists of MIGS, MIMS and MIMARKS standards and describes fourteen environments. MIGS, MIMS and MIMARKS share common mandatory core descriptors, differ in standard-specific elements and can be tailored to a particular environment by a subset of relevant environment-specific information components.

General data

All variables and parameters (measurement attributes) must be documented with an attribute name and attribute definition that provides a human-readable context for the measurement. For numeric data, attributes must include the units of measurement using SI unit definitions. Where non-SI units are used, a mapping to SI units must be provided that includes a) a unit name, b) a unit definition, c) a unit notation abbreviation, d) the unit's parent SI unit name, e) a multiplier to the parent SI unit. For numerical data without a unit (e.g., percent, count x per count y, etc.), the unit should be noted as "dimensionless". For non-numeric, categorical data, coded values must be defined in a code/definition list, or be defined by an external, controlled vocabulary term. We recommend the NERC Vocabulary Standard. The NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS) web service provides access to controlled vocabularies via an international, actively-contributing research community

- What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

When possible, open-source tools and open data formats will be used and all necessary documentation will be made available

- Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Currently not available

- Where will the documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.

Whenever possible, documentation and code will be hosted on a GitHub repository. This approach facilitates version control, open access, collaboration, and long-term hosting.

Additionally, it is possible to link specific versions to DOIs using Zenodo, ensuring proper citation and easy reference.

Making data interoperable

- The data management guidelines document the specific meta-information surrounding the data that is needed. Please specify how you plan to capture and store the specified individual meta-information elements.

Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

- How will the data be licensed to permit the widest (by any party) re-use possible?

The use of Creative Commons licenses is strongly encouraged within the project to promote open access and data sharing. Specifically, the CC0 (Public Domain Dedication) and CC BY (Attribution) licenses are recommended. These licenses ensure that data can be freely used, distributed, and built upon by others, while giving appropriate credit to the original creators.

- When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

A reasonable timeframe should be discussed with the involved researchers.

Data security

- What provisions are in place for data security (including backups, secure storage and transfer)?

For all data, an attempt will be made to follow the 3-2-1 (3 copies, 2 media types, 1 external location) rule. During the cruise, this might not be possible for all data. Even after the cruise, this might be challenging for the biggest datasets.

General procedures

- Logbooks: Hard copies of logbooks will be completed daily by the members.
- Spreadsheets: Data from the logbooks will be digitized into data template in tidy format daily by the members, proofread by the designated data responsible for each team.
- Backup procedures: Logbooks will be scanned, and digital data will be backed up daily on 2 computers and 2 external hard drives.
- Data on AWI server
- Metadata directory

Ethical aspects

- Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

Other issues

- On top of the infrastructure and procedures that WOBECC provides, which national/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management are you following?

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